

CHESS SETUP: STEP 4

CHESS SETUP getting bigger and brighter

Welcome to our 4th newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

The European project investigating **buildings'**
energy self-sufficiency

CHESS SETUP on its team

Revision meeting at the EC in Brussels

The partners gathered in Brussels last March to review the work carried out during the past 21 months. The project is still moving forward, all three pilots are being built under the requirements of CHESS SETUP's partners from Corby (UK), to Sant Cugat del Vallès and Manlleu (Spain).

Considering the limitations of the pilots in practice, the possibilities of optimizing the CHESS SETUP system for each scenario are considered and analyzed in more detail.

CHESS SETUP on site

Corby finally springing up

As expected, the work started in Corby: the first plot foundations were marked for concrete and Earth Energy Bank (to store energy and adapt its usage to the demand) paving the way for the future 47 ecohomes.

Other pilots also moving forward

Sant Cugat

In the Spanish sport centre, the tendering procedure is ongoing: the administrative process was successfully completed, the construction company was chosen and the scheduled work will soon be defined. The construction process should certainly start in the coming month.

Lavola's headquarters

In Manlleu, facing the practical limitations, the CHESSE 3.0 was finally retained as final scheme and is currently implemented. After replacing the solar hybrid panels by photovoltaic ones from CHESSE 1.0 to CHESSE 2.0, CHESSE 3.0 replaced the water tanks by energy storage in mortar slabs.

CHESSE SETUP online

” **How to retrofit European buildings and reduce their energy dependency?**

4 European projects (H2020)
CHESS SETUP
THERMOS
OptEEmAL
TESSe2b

Share experiences!

Wednesday, June 20th
11 - 12:15 AM (Paris time)

First Webinar proudly and successfully managed

Our first Webinar on Energy Retrofitting took place on June 20th. It reminded the latest progresses of CHESS SETUP and introduced three other educative experiences to learn and discuss the best practices towards energy sufficiency. We thank again our counterparts from THERMOS, OptEEmAL and TESSe2b projects for their enriching presentations that you can discover [here](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=eYdQOTWWC851SyXD6hOjTfqRy40Eq3J7QzGxnt4w-Kl.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAubmV0L25ld3Mtc29jaWFsliwicil6ljM5MjBLYmFhLTQ5ODQtNDYwMi05NDM0LTVjZWZmZDFiNDU0ZiIsIm0iOiJscCJ9) (<https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=eYdQOTWWC851SyXD6hOjTfqRy40Eq3J7QzGxnt4w-Kl.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAubmV0L25ld3Mtc29jaWFsliwicil6ljM5MjBLYmFhLTQ5ODQtNDYwMi05NDM0LTVjZWZmZDFiNDU0ZiIsIm0iOiJscCJ9>).

A brand-new LinkedIn page

All the team is also very proud to introduce its newly created [LinkedIn page](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=Ck7511vUg5708_oyXa7iV3eIzXNIUCJiQbL7O82BCdl.eyJ1ljoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cubGlua2VkaW4uY29tL2NvbXBhbnkvY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAvliwicil6ImNkNjRjMjY5LTJmMjUtNDgzMy02YzdlLWI4NTBiYzBkYzE4Mlslm0iOiJscCJ9) (https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=Ck7511vUg5708_oyXa7iV3eIzXNIUCJiQbL7O82BCdl.eyJ1ljoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cubGlua2VkaW4uY29tL2NvbXBhbnkvY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAvliwicil6ImNkNjRjMjY5LTJmMjUtNDgzMy02YzdlLWI4NTBiYzBkYzE4Mlslm0iOiJscCJ9) which aim is to offer an always more exhaustive view of the promising advances of CHESS SETUP. Do not hesitate to subscribe to the latest news.

*"One of the things that can be done to boost energy efficiency is **creating awareness** and realising that **reducing energy use will have multiple benefits**, such as lower cost of the energy transition, reduced energy bills for the most vulnerable, a more lenient and competitive EU economy, higher quality of life and cleaner air and environment."*

Mechthild Wörsdörfer, (<https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=-TAs7ileYTAAbJqiJvihwzfbtUpiAwUohXmoNXkYnkMc.eyJ1ljoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZlVzZXcuZXUvliwicil6ljhjNzlyY2ZmLWFKYjgtNDMyNS0xYzEwLTg3YjY1Y2M1NzVknYlslm0iOiJscCJ9>) Director in charge of renewables, research and innovation, energy efficiency, DG Energy, European Commission

And what else on the European energy efficiency scene?

International Conference on Renewable Energy

On April 25-27, the ICREN 2018 gathered, in Barcelona (Spain), researches of the Renewable Energy field from 41 countries to have a global overview of the latest progress towards a better future. CHESS SETUP was there, represented by the Sant Cugat City Council.

IV Congreso Ciudades Inteligentes

Madrid welcomed the fourth CongresoCI last May 30-31 to assemble the whole smart cities' Spanish community. It showed, once again, the Spanish commitment to implementing and spreading the good practices in terms of smart cities' and buildings' solutions for reducing energy consumption.

41ST IAEE
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
GRONINGEN 2018

**IV CONGRESO
EDIFICIOS INTELIGENTES**
Madrid 19 Junio 2018

IAEE International Conference

The 41st International Association for Energy Economics (IAEE) International Conference also took place from June 10 to 13 in Groningen (the Netherlands). Academics, policy makers, consultants, and representatives from energy businesses had the chance to share and discuss today's energy question in the world.

IV Congreso Edificios Inteligentes

Last June's CongresoEI was another occasion to prove Spain's leadership in promoting and setting up promising projects in the building sector for energy self-sufficiency. It was held in Madrid and brought together the most important actors of the field to have a look at the future and opportunities of Smart Buildings.

Sustainable Energy Week

The theme of this year's EUSEW is "Lead the clean energy transition". It was held in early June in Brussels to offer innovative ideas towards energy transition to new EU Member States and discuss the current issues related to the topic.

A new EC regulation for Energy Performance in Buildings in July?

The revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive will enter into force as of 9 July 2018. It has huge potential for efficiency gains in the EU building sector and includes measures that will accelerate the rate of building renovation and smarter new buildings.

Click [here](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=4cgmSvVY78JNXr9V2NWw1XgVBOAivVfiQrjIAZWLEJQ.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cDovL2V1cm9wYS5ldS9yYXBpZC9wcmVzcy1yZWxlYXNlX1NUQVRFTUV0VC0xOC0zOTk3X2VuLmh0bSIsInliOiIwYTlmNGYzOS1kZWZlLTRiMzktYjIhZC0yZGU3YTJlNWVmNWliLCJtIjoibHAifQ) (https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=4cgmSvVY78JNXr9V2NWw1XgVBOAivVfiQrjIAZWLEJQ.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cDovL2V1cm9wYS5ldS9yYXBpZC9wcmVzcy1yZWxlYXNlX1NUQVRFTUV0VC0xOC0zOTk3X2VuLmh0bSIsInliOiIwYTlmNGYzOS1kZWZlLTRiMzktYjIhZC0yZGU3YTJlNWVmNWliLCJtIjoibHAifQ) for more info.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

For more information about the project, you can find us on,

- Our [webpage](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=xxOSMOCOwFQ4AxTWedDViEoChqPa_rlam0dJcIRTj8U.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAubmV0LyIsInliOiJhMmRmNTJmNC0xMDFjLTQwODktZjEyYS0xNTZkM2E5NWE3OWQiLCJtIjoibHAifQ) (https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?

w=xxOSMOCOwFQ4AxTWedDViEoChqPa_rlam0dJcIRTj8U.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAubmV0LyIsInliOiJhMmRmNTJmNC0xMDFjLTQwODktZjEyYS0xNTZkM2E5NWE3OWQiLCJtIjoibHAifQ)

- Our Twitter account [@ChessSetup](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=pbYoOhbnbO2tJN3YeZSFZ3OCiHzh9e-3tYWT6AIsdpU.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly90d2l0dGVyLmNvbS9DaGVzYz1NldHVwliwici6lmeYzGY1MmY0LTEwMWMtNDA4OS1mMTJhLTE1NmQzYTkyYTk5ZCIsIm0iOiJscCJ9) (https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?

w=pbYoOhbnbO2tJN3YeZSFZ3OCiHzh9e-

3tYWT6AIsdpU.eyJ1IjoiaHR0cHM6Ly90d2l0dGVyLmNvbS9DaGVzYz1NldHVwliwici6lmeYzGY1MmY0LTEwMWMtNDA4OS1mMTJhLTE1NmQzYTkyYTk5ZCIsIm0iOiJscCJ9)

- Our [LinkedIn](https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=-plI0Yhfb5mPVmHMMCr6-82khsYFfA7hx5qi3qqW70Y.eyJ1ljoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cubGlua2VkaW4uY29tL2NvbXBhbmkvY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAvliwicil6ImEyZGY1MmY0LTEwMWMtNDA4OS1mMTJhLTE1NmQzYTk1YTc5ZCIsIm0iOiJscCJ9) (https://shoutout.wix.com/so/9MGtLkoU/c?w=-plI0Yhfb5mPVmHMMCr6-82khsYFfA7hx5qi3qqW70Y.eyJ1ljoiaHR0cHM6Ly93d3cubGlua2VkaW4uY29tL2NvbXBhbmkvY2hlc3Mtc2V0dXAvliwicil6ImEyZGY1MmY0LTEwMWMtNDA4OS1mMTJhLTE1NmQzYTk1YTc5ZCIsIm0iOiJscCJ9) page

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